

IMPORTANCE OF INTEGRATION IN NEW GENERATION TEXTBOOKS OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

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Abstract. *In the period of primary education, a child requires careful attention. At this moment, the child as a student, feels interest and love for school and education, and in the path of knowledge begins to gather strength for future results. In this article, the possibilities of forming 4C skills in elementary school students are outlined. Also, this article provides tips on how to organize lessons effectively based on an integrated approach. In lessons organized in an integrated way, students learn these topics quickly and easily, and they remain in their memories for a long time.*

Keywords: *primary education, national curriculum, 4C model, collaboration, creativity, critical thinking, communication, integration.*

Developments are taking place on all fronts in "New Uzbekistan" today. In particular, in order to fundamentally improve the quality of education, curricula, methodological manuals for teachers are adapted to advanced international criteria, instead of the state education standard in primary grades, based on advanced foreign experience, "National curriculum" is being introduced, which does not overload the child. Such changes in the primary education system make the lessons more interactive and effective. Also, there are topics and exercises aimed at implementing the integration process in the lesson, which expand the student's worldview. Quality education in schools largely depend on the textbooks being created. That is, it should meet the educational standards, interest the student and arouse his love for science.

On May 11, 2022, it was approved by the presidential decree "On approval of the national program for the development of public education in 2022-2026". The National Curriculum is a document that provides guidance in explaining the outcomes expected of students at the end of each grade level and the transition from one grade to the next grade and what the student should achieve and the assessment process. In the national curriculum, the following take a leading place: consistency, coherence, continuity, socio-economic development of society, development of science and advanced technologies, adaptation of educational content to world educational standards, taking into account the current state of international education standards, ensuring integration of science and education. The national educational programs, which began to be created in 2020, defined the skills that should be formed in students based on the needs of the 21st century.

Forward-thinking, persistent, goal-oriented, independent decision-making, and positive problem-solving individuals are needed for the development of society. Such individuals can develop the economy, manage society, and change our lives. In the national curriculum, efforts are being made to educate such individuals by instilling 21st century skills.

The rapid development of science and technology, the globalization of the world, and the development of information and communication technologies change people's worldview, ways

of achieving success, human talent, ability, and social activity serve as the basis of society. This situation is one of the tasks of our state to form every student in the society to be competitive in the society, to adapt to the changing socio-economic environment, to be active, socially competent, possessing high-level knowledge, mentally and spiritually.

As it is known, in accordance with the tasks defined in the concept of development of the public education system until 2030, based on advanced foreign experiences, 1st-4th grade textbooks were newly prepared on the basis of the "4C" model. The use of the "4C" model has undergone many tests. This modern approach is successfully implemented in countries with advanced education such as Singapore, China, England, Finland, and Estonia. Also, in the education of countries that have high positions in international rankings such as PISA and PIRLS, special emphasis is placed on skills such as communication, research, creativity, which include the "4C" model, and that is why they achieve great results in international rankings.[1]

In the new experiment implemented in the primary classes of our country, more importance is attached to the critical thinking of students and the ability to express their opinion freely. This methodology is aimed at comprehensive development of children and includes four main competencies.

Collaboration - designed to help students develop teamwork skills. It helps students learn the skills of collaboration, effective communication, and mutual support.

Communication - develops students' ability to communicate with others. Students learn to express their thoughts clearly and obviously, to listen and understand the interlocutor, and to effectively use language tools in conveying information.

Creativity - develops the ability to think creatively and innovate. Students learn to use new approaches to achieve their goals, develop innovative solutions, and acquire creative problem-solving skills.

Critical thinking - this methodology involves the development of students' skills to critically evaluate information, form their own opinions and judgments. Students learn to approach problems from an analytical point of view and form their own point of view based on logical thinking.

If we want to develop these important competencies, we need to organize the educational process in an interesting and useful way for children. Each lesson at school is a process in which students not only master the content of science, but also acquire independent knowledge and develop their abilities. In general, these innovations serve to create a more effective, modern and

person-oriented educational environment, and create a basis for the development of personal qualities of students, providing them with deep knowledge and skills.[3]

Attention to the state of the educational environment, methods of organizing the educational process, technologies and methods of teaching and training professional skills, forms of interaction with students in the development of "4C" competencies in primary grades we have to focus. It is also necessary to approach the assessment of "4C" competencies creatively, but at the same time, one should not forget about the assessment of consequences, benefits and risks, and most importantly, responsibility for the results of one's work. Traditional education teaches sequential problem solving, breaking them down into manageable tasks. But in modern societies, this is not enough.

Nowadays, it is much more important to have a broad worldview, to synthesize ideas from different fields of knowledge, and to discover ambiguous connections. Traditional education relies on individual student efforts and individual assessment of achievement. In modern conditions, this is not enough.

Children's mental state is also taken into account when developing textbooks. They make extensive use of pictures and illustrations to enhance creativity and thinking skills. Scientific studies show that a child receives information faster through images than through text. Therefore, in creating new textbooks, along with texts, special attention is paid to pictures. There are six graphic characters in the new textbooks. They talk to students in absentia during the lesson.

Textbooks characters

The main tool of the teacher is the textbook. Current textbooks are created on the basis of the latest advanced pedagogical technologies. If we take the alphabet book, the exercise book is adapted to it, that is, it goes parallel to each other. The exercise is not only writing in notebooks, students also learn to think logically: they find missing letters, words, and make sentences based on pictures. Adapted to creative thinking and expression of thoughts from the time of the alphabet. When writing essays, 3D pictures are given, on the basis of which the child can describe his thoughts. In general, the textbooks are made in a way that a child can understand, with a creative approach. The topics covered in the 1st grade are repeated in the following grades. Information about these topics is expanding and becoming more scientific

Another novelty of these textbooks is that, for example, in mathematics textbooks there are a lot of example-problems aimed at logical thinking and students' work on themselves. In addition to the main topic, a side topic is also used in the textbook. If we are talking about measurements,

information such as the area of the Republic of Uzbekistan, regions, and the number of rivers given as a related topic. This situation directly creates integration between disciplines. In the textbooks of the new generation, all subjects are closely related to each other, that is, they complement each other.

Integrating subjects in elementary grades increases the efficiency of the lesson, leads to efficient use of time, helps to learn the lesson in depth, increases free time and involves in clubs. It is possible to integrate mother language, reading, science, art and technology lessons in primary education. For example, in 3rd grade, topic 1 is about the homeland, and the same topic is given in the textbooks of reading, science, mother language and mathematics. Let's go through these tutorials one by one. In the reading book, the 1st theme is " Our country is in our hearts ", a text about the homeland, vocabulary words related to it, and various tasks are given. In mother language book, the main topic is "Speech", and all exercises related to the topic, the homeland, state symbols, symbols of our homeland are given. In the mathematics textbook, the main topic is "Numbers from 1 to 100", and the related topic is the Republic of Uzbekistan. The problems, examples, diagrams, and tables on the topic are given about the cities, rivers, nature of our country, and the general areas of the regions. The theme of the Science textbook is "Remembering Summer", the questions, assignments, pictures depict beautiful places of our country, the deserts of Uzbekistan and a map. This helps the child to better understand the subject, allows him to understand it more widely and deeply, and helps him to remember it for a long time. This increases the effectiveness of the lesson.

A good result is achieved even if mother language, reading, mathematics, and technology lessons are integrated. In this case, the student understands the lesson well. For example, if the topic "Autumn" is taught, the topic is read, explained, issues related to harvesting are solved, fruits can be made in technology classes. Then it makes it possible for them to master the lesson perfectly. For example, students picked 35 kg of apples on the first day, and 45 kg on the second day in the garden. How many kilos of apples did they pick in total? Based on this problem, they can draw a picture of fruits. In one lesson, the children learned about autumn, learned about fruits and drew a picture, solved a problem about autumn fruits. In this way, the students get a lot of information through integration in one lesson and remembers it for a long time. Mathematics,

physical education, science, and music lessons will be useful if they are incorporated. Listening to music, solving problems related to the topic, making things all will lead to an interesting result.

However, the following points should be paid attention to when the lessons are taught by integrating the subjects:

each lesson should be aimed at a specific goal;

selected additional material related to interdisciplinary relations must be connected with the subject.

In conclusion, integration expands the existing topic, requires deep analysis, summarizes phenomena, their scope of knowledge expands at the expense of other disciplines. In turn, the integrated lesson requires additional training, great knowledge, and high professional skills from the teacher. The main feature of the integrated lesson is that such a lesson is based on one topic, it is the main focus, the rest are integrated with it, the processes in learning, it is used to understand the meaning of the subject, to understand its relationship with life, and to use the acquired knowledge in practice.

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